

Demet Kocatepe*

Sinop University, School of Tourism and Hotel Management, Department of Food & Beverage Management, Sinop, Turkey

Dates: Received: 24 May, 2017; Accepted: 25 July, 2017; Published: 26 July, 2017

***Corresponding author:** Demet Kocatepe, Sinop University, School of Tourism and Hotel Management, Department of Food & Beverage Management, Sinop, Turkey, Tel: +90 0368 2715785; E mail: dkocatepe@sinop.edu.tr

Keywords: Food security, Tourism sector, Catering, Food poisoning

<https://www.peertechz.com>

Short Communication

Food security in Food & Beverage sector

Abstract

The education level of people throughout the world increases food safety awareness is also increasing. In tourism sector, the investments to food security is increasing and applied to a variety of educational activities. Every year there are many food poisoning cases resulting and a part of in death in the world. Such serious incidents were observed in facilities such as hotels specifically catering service provided leads to both prestige and economic losses. In this study the cases of food poisoning occurred throughout the world and are given information about their effects on the tourism industry.

Introduction

Food and drink is one of the daily basic needs of people. The desire to eat everything that flavor, usually it reduces the dangerous misconception to people, it's headed for unhealthy foods with excessive and balanced nutrition. With the rapid increases in industrialization, women are also entering the work life, increase the family income and reduction of the time spent with family, all of them have been accustomed to individuals to live and consumption fast-food outside the home, as a consequence of them catering sector has emerged. However, individuals throughout the year will be to establish the dream of vacation in the rapidly intensifying work life. Even the all year round peoples are exploring the places where they stay for a week or ten days and they throw stress. Therefore, being high exceptions of tourists coming to the hospitality business, in addition to physical structure of the plant, they give the importance to food and beverage services. The industry of food and beverage services in the hospitality is a part of catering sector and the most important and sensitive point is the health of guests in this sector. There are many firms in the sector to produce in optimal conditions. The food are produced in unhealthy operates which we eat in the fact that they have many microorganisms and cause food poisoning.

After a certain period of time after eating the food, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, headache, and sometimes fever, vision, hearing and nervous system disorders that cause certain health problem or diseases are called as food poisoning. Microbial agents of food-borne illness are bacteria, protozoa and parasites, toxins and viruses. CDC (Centers for disease control and prevention center) reported that in the World 76 million people had a foodborne illness and 325 thousand of these patients admitted the hospital that 5000 was the fatal. In addition that, according to the CDC data's, only in 2008 in

the United State, total 1034 food poisoning cases was observed and the 1276 patients were affected by the case (23152 patients) were admitted to hospital and 22 patients died. The major effect of the more than half of food poisoning cases in 1034 were ready meals, salads and patisserie products. Norwalk-type virus was through the people by the cross-contamination. In this case derived from 15% poultry meat, 14% red meat, 14% fish and a great majority (57%) foods served as a cold for example; salad, cake and other patisserie products. Also, 62% of patients applied to the hospital (1276 patients) had been identified Salmonella which is an important role in food poisoning and that does not cause changes in taste and smell of food [1].

In the world in many countries, food poisoning data have been regularly record since 1996. In our country, food poisoning data have been only record if the patient presented to the emergency department. According to the TUIK data between the years 1993-2005, 108.246 patient hospitalized due to food poisoning and 1072 patient of them dead [2].

New trends have emerged in the food production and use in spite of the rise in living standards with industrialization. Consumers canalize to take -home foods and as a result of this, new industries produced and prepare different foods have developed. In this case, the importance of food control service which improved features has also increased.

Today, old-fashioned food processing and consumer awareness of the need to offer consumers in both countries approach food laws "more healthy and safe food production" due to updates in line with many significant changes have occurred and food safety issues has been the most important social issues in recent years. Food safety is defined as; the taking of observance and action in the food production, processing,

storage, transport and distribution phase for production of food to ensure healthy

Food safety today, not only in developed countries but also around the world, is recognized as an international standard and requirements and in many countries it is considered as a prerequisite for reducing production costs, increasing productivity, developing of import and export.

In the world significant developments being experienced in the national and international tourism activity with the effects of globalization. Nutrition is a people's most basic need and this need is great importance, because of sector especially climate change and individuals differences in the food culture in the tourism. The foods offered in the food and beverage sector should be safe as well as well as being tasty and flashy. In the food and beverage organizations, food hygiene and safety, in other words, food and beverage prepared in accordance with the prescribed standard of health is very important in terms of customer health and satisfaction.

Tourism activities in a rapid growth worldwide significantly contributes to the economy of Turkey. In parallel, improving the quality and safety of food and drinks offered in this companies, it requires that services be offered in addition to the hygienic conditions. On food safety in the kitchen of a catering unit, which also accommodation establishments are required to audit and training needs. There is a need to stay in the kitchens of the food safety auditing and training requirements.

Foodborne poisoning employees up front from top to bottom within the industry to be able to switch all staff must be knowledgeable about food safety and quality. Food poisoning and food-borne diseases in tourism sector primarily reduces the work efficiency and causes a loss of prestige and demand in the enterprise sector. The most important point to protect the health of tourists in the tourism sector is to give importance to the general rules of hygiene and sanitation. What images and excellent service in a facility built with the latest technology, no matter how good the poor quality of food and beverages can cause guests to leave the negative thoughts from businesses. Amateurish applied hygiene rules rather than deliberately to follow every stage and must first know the causes of food poisoning observed in the sector.

The main causes of food poisoning in the sector:

- Food preparation long before the time of consumption of food
- Perishable, to keep foods which have high protein content (meat, poultry, fish, milk, ...) at room temperature (20-40°C) for a long time, that must be stored in the cold
- Before placing hot food in the refrigerator to be cooled very slowly: for example, keeping the mouth closed deep containers
- Food have not been heated to a high temperature enough to kill bacteria for re-heating consumption
- Food infected with bacteria before and spoiled to be given to the consumer

- To consumption of undercooked chicken and meat dishes
- To make solution treatment in the suboptimal conditions (for example, leave room temperature to dissolve the above clearly)
- Cooked foods to be contaminated with the bacteria from raw foods, through a variety of equipment or employees
- To keep the hot dishes below 65°C
- The staff which do not comply with hygiene rules and that move bacteria (disease-causing microorganisms, viruses etc.) to the foods [3].

Conclusion

Aiming to provide modern services in today's conditions, with kitchen and service departments of the hospitality business professionals, within the framework of hygiene and sanitation in food production and delivery, in standard sizes and risks also aims to minimize the Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points) is implementing the system. ISO 22000 Food Safety System is effective and important method of ensuring food safety, to play an active role in the destruction of microbiological, physical and chemical hazards in the food and beverage industry. The most important point to protect the health of tourists in the tourism sector is to give importance to the general rules of hygiene and sanitation. A catering business owner, if you want the business of being consistently hygienic production standards making and safety of the products it offers to prepare guests for Food Safety should establish the control system, should provide continuity and support. The basic problems of this sector cannot provide the low quality of education related personnel and training continuity, quality and the same standard in the supply of raw materials and unfair competition in relation to marketing, quality / price balance and control of failure and to continue with the continuous improvement will be established for Food Safety and with the quality Management System will be exceeded. To comply with hygiene rules is of great importance in hotels. Remember that hygiene can be a food poisoning can be experienced in the hotel due to non-compliance, lead poisoning is not product brand, and the hotel's name comes to the fore.

References

1. Anonymous 2012 (2012) [Link: https://goo.gl/SVSfcw](https://goo.gl/SVSfcw)
2. TUIK 2012 (2012) Selected 150 Breakdown Cause Diseases of the Hospital Inpatient. [Link: https://goo.gl/Q54cFn](https://goo.gl/Q54cFn)
3. Mahmutoğlu T (2007) Producing "Safe Food" in Food Industry. HACCP: "Hazard analysis-critical control points" system, ISO 22000: "Food safety management system requirements for any organization in the food chain" standard. ODTÜ Gelistrime Vakfı Publishing and Communication Inc. Publications, ODTÜ Yayıncılık. 312.